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Brief history of the island of New Guinea (Papua)

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Abstract

Papua Island is divided into two parts, the eastern part of which is within the continental landmass of Australia, and the western part is located within Indonesia. The two departments are governed in many respects by both. Pacific Islands, and New Guinea.

Keywords: Brief history; Island; New Guinea; Iraq

1. Introduction

Logos of New Guinea, New Guinea, 7.5 million people little and count. The country enjoys abundant natural resources, and is close to the fast-growing Asian markets. The population is remarkably diverse, speaking more than 800 languages [1].

The meaning of the word idiomatically, it is taken from the Malay language buawa-bua, and means black man with thick curly hair. And there was a large area of neighboring buildings, and within the neighboring buildings, and inside the next room, a common language, through which people of different tongues could communicate, but in the western part, who are the inhabitants of Irian, many of them speak the Malay language or what is known as the second Malay language [4]. Teachers are the main caregivers and the first line of protection for school children Their role complements that of parents. During school hours, school teachers are actually the first-respondent in cases of disasters or emergencies. They must be able to deal properly with health emergencies both in normal children, and those children with special health care needs [5].

2. Methodology

Most of the inhabitants of Papua Island lived since ancient times in rural communities spread widely in the high mountains to avoid exposure to the raids that usually occur among them, however, reliable population data is not available in the first years of the arrival of Europeans, as a result of the many deaths due to malaria , which killed many of them. However, one of the important features of the population distribution in Papua has been calculated according to the most dense areas (more than two hundred people per square kilometer, and sometimes exceeding a thousand), that is, in the form of small groups scattered among the high valleys, and on the volcanic islands, including Buka), and the Gazelle Peninsula, and southern Bougainville, and Biak), and on some areas of the slopes of the Huon Peninsula, and coconut palm lands with a relatively high population density (Gulf of Papua), and there are large lands Very uninhabited.

Since the arrival of the Spanish explorer Inigo Ortiz de Retiz, to the island of Papua in the year 1545, he called it (Guinea Nueva) or (New Guinea) because he drew his attention to the physiological similarity between the inhabitants of Papua and the inhabitants of Guinea in West Africa.

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The island of Papua was not a place of attraction and interest for the trips of the major colonial powers, until the seventeenth century, when those countries began to pay increasing attention to the island because of the occurrence of two important developments, the first of which: the escalating conflict during the first half of that century, between the Sultans of the islands of Tidore and Ternate for hegemony over Maritime navigation, and the second: European merchants raced to reach the Spice Islands, which put them in a state of intense competition among themselves to control those islands, especially Papua.

Despite recent strong economic growth, more than 3 million people live below the national poverty line, most of them in rural areas. Young people in particular face limited opportunities in rural areas, where many of them have had no formal education. Inequality remains endemic in Papua New Guinea; It is estimated that 20 percent of the population earns 80 percent of the total income. A large majority of the population (87 per cent) lives in rural areas and depends mainly on semi-subsistence farming.

Agriculture accounts for about a third of the gross domestic product and employs 80 percent of the workforce. Smallholder farming systems dominate the sector.

3. Results and discussion

Coffee and cocoa represent the two most important cash crops, and half of the total labor force works in their production. Contributing to low yields are the cost and availability of modern inputs and technologies, lack of irrigation water, and poor access to support services. The World Bank estimates that coffee yields have declined by between 30 and 50 percent due to a lack of support services and inefficient farming techniques. Logistical costs are high due to poor transportation network and lack of market organization and market information, which are disincentive factors for small farmers.

Agricultural development is hampered by weather phenomena and hazards related to climate change. This included since the earliest frosts caused by El Nino, which affected a third of the population. As a result, more than 1 million people face serious levels of food insecurity in fragile parts of the highlands and lowlands.

As for study and education, the education system in western Irian expanded rapidly under the Indonesian administration, which took control of the island of Irian in 1962. But primary school enrollment in 1972 (123,700) was more than double the level in 1961. Although there was rapid growth in government primary schools. In 1970, 80 percent of district enrollments were in mission schools. In other Indonesian provinces, most primary school enrollments are in public schools. Bahasa Indonesia is the language of instruction in all schools.

Although primary school enrollment in kabupaten highland in Jayawijaya increased eightfold between 1961 and 1969. Jayawijaya was only a third of the district average in the latter year. In 1969, all but two hundred of the 6,600 school enrollments in Jayawijaya were in primary schools [3].

Secondary school enrollment in the county has grown at a faster rate, although there are still very few places for all primary school graduates. The expansion of state vocational schools has been particularly rapid. The Department of Agriculture operated a number of small schools of forestry, agriculture and animal husbandry and their graduates were quickly appointed to public service positions [3].

In conjunction with the rapid expansion of education, there has been some discussion about the major problems in the education system. The content and logic of primary education is taken from other parts of Indonesia. The main focus is on providing inputs into higher education and on meeting the assumed needs of the public service.

Vocational training was an important part of education efforts. Apart from the vocational schools run by the Departments of Education and Agriculture. The Workforce Administration conducts many short courses in writing. Ceramic. Cabinet industry. Mechanical work and other topics. At the request of officials kabupaten. Mobile training units have moved to most urban centers to provide training courses. Many government departments have organized short courses aimed at upgrading the skills of their employees.

Some mission schools also have a strong vocational focus. Especially in the south. Despite the lack of teaching aids and equipment. The Catholic mission of Merauke made a great contribution to the popularization of simple artisans. Especially housing construction. skills.

The Jayapura Vocational Training Center was the main recipient of Fundwi's education allocation. .29 The VTC has more advanced equipment than that used in any workshop in Irian Jaya, perhaps in all of Indonesia. P? An expat instructor told us that the teaching aids used in the auto shop were comparable to the best available in Europe. Seven foreign employees were employed in 1972. As late as 1972 169 students were taught in two-year courses in automobiles, machine shop, electricity, woodworking, carpentry and masonry trades. Nearly all sophomores and 90 percent of first-year students are native Irianians. 59 trainees were to graduate at the end of 1972.

Neither the teachers' background nor the teaching aids allow them to impart skills that can be applied directly in the small workshops that serve the cities. Building cycles have been adapted to closely fit local practices, but the Foundation does not readily adapt to local needs. Large mining companies offer the only job opportunities for apprentices in the motor and machinery trade.

4. Conclusion

Papua Island is divided into two parts, the eastern part of which is within the continental landmass of Australia, and the western part is located within Indonesia. The two departments are governed in many respects by both. Pacific Islands, and New Guinea

And benefit society through the culture of peoples

Compliance with ethical standards

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